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Development And Evaluation Of Dietary Weaning Formulations From Millets, Soybeans, Groundnut And Sorghum For Enhanced Infant Nutrition

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ABSTRACT

Malnutrition affect millions of infants and young children globally. Weaning foods can bridge nutritional gaps, but commercial options are often unaffordable and inadequate. This research aimed to develop and evaluate a weaning diet formulation using millet, soybeans, groundnut and sorghum to provide a nutritious, locally sourced, and cost-effective solution. The research analyzed the macro and micro nutrient, anti-nutritional factors and effects of processing methods on the formulated weaning diet. Results showed that the selected food staples are rich in macro and micro nutrient, but also contain anti nutritional factors. The formulated weaning diet demonstrated improved nutritional profiles, with enhanced levels of micro and macro nutrient. Processing method reduced anti nutritional factors and improved nutrient bioavailability. This study provides valuable insights into development of nutritious and acceptable weaning diet, highlighting the importance of proper processing and formulation to minimize anti nutritional factors and optimize nutrient bioavailability.

Keywords weaning diet, millets, soybeans, groundnut, and sorghum.

INTRODUCTION

A natural and age-old method of newborn nutrition has been breastfeeding. Human breast milk has been the foundation of human life since the beginning of time, promoting growth and development all the way up to weaning age and beyond. Similar to other nations, Nigeria has seen a decline in the length of time that infants are breastfed throughout time as a result of illnesses, diseases, changes in maternal mortality, and inconveniences (Ella *et al.*, 2016; Maharlouei *et al.*, 2018; Aghae *et al.*, 2019). Infants should be exclusively breastfed for at least six months, and then they should be fed a supplemental diet along with breast milk for the next eighteen months or longer (WHO, 2021). Beginning at six months of age, an infant's demand for micronutrients like iron and zinc rises quickly (WHO, 2021). Complementary diets also fill the gap in the infant's mineral needs and help manage and nourish infants who are extra sick or under stress, even though exclusive breastfeeding offers immunity from diseases and meets the infant's nutritional needs (Abeshu *et al.*, 2016; Paintal and Aguayo, 2016; WHO, 2001; USDA and USDH and HS, 2020; Savarino *et al.*, 2021).

Commercial weaning meals are widely available; these are the results of years of research and development, and are primarily of foreign origin. However, issues with accessibility, acceptability, and pricing restrict the adoption of these foods locally. These foods may cause problems in certain infants, or they may not even be edible to them. Additionally, the typical family cannot afford the high expense of commercial weaning foods. This has made it necessary to rely on locally produced, inadequate nutrient-

rich weaning food. During the weaning period, the accompanying baby malnourishment usually lead to fast weight loss and poor physical and mental development (Udoh and Amodu, 2016; Jahan *et al.*, 2021). The work presented here aimed to produce a weaning formulated local diet from the combination of millet, soybeans, groundnut and Sorghum.

Weaning meals in Nigeria are typically made with guinea corn, millet, or maize as the base cereal. Different regions and tribes in the nation have different names for the gruels made from these fermented cereals, such as Akamu (Igbo), Kunu (Hausa), and Ogi (Yoruba). The majority of families feed their newborns gruels without providing enough supplementation because of financial problems, poverty and ignorance (Abeshu *et al.*, 2016). According to Abeshu *et al.*, (2016), these diets are low in nutrients and can cause severe nutritional disorders in certain cases. According to Egbujie and Okoye (2019), crayfish, groundnuts, or soybeans, either separately or in combination, are typically added to enrich the weaning food. Inclusion of cereals, legumes, vegetables, and fruits in weaning foods has been suggested (UNICEF, 2020) and has been reported to make a good diet (Ibironke *et al.*, 2014; Kumari and Sangeetha, 2017; Iwanegbe, 2021). Therefore, in order for a locally prepared weaning food to fulfill its intended function, it must include the proper combination of nutrients that may give the baby a sufficient amount of nutrition. In addition to having the proper ratios of fats, carbohydrates, and proteins, the proper amounts of minerals and vitamins should also be present to prevent deficiencies and stunted development. Furthermore, by utilizing the proper ratio and avoiding ingredients that could not improve the food's total nutritional value, this type of weaning food formulation should be able to attain acceptability and cost. Evaluating the approximate mineral and anti-nutritional makeup of food samples and diet plans is very important to achieving these goals (Ogbonnaya *et al.*, 2023).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The proximate analysis and anti-nutritional factor of this research experiment was conducted at the Department of Biochemistry Laboratory, and mineral analysis of this research experiment was conducted at the central Laboratory of Umaru Musa Yaradua University, Katsina state.

Sample Selection and Preparation

Millet, soybeans, groundnut, and Sorghum were purchased from the central market, Katsina State, All the samples were kept in the Department of Biochemistry, Umaru Musa Yaradua University, Katsina state, prior to preparation and analysis.

Preparation of sample flour

The samples (soybeans, sorghum, and groundnut) were sorted for stones, rot, and other physical defects. The one without defects was cleaned, milled with a hammer mill, and sieved to obtain the flour.

Proximate Analyses:

Proximate Analysis:

Samples of the dietary formulation were analyzed for proximate composition using the appropriate method described by AOAC (2012). This includes the determination of moisture, crude fiber, protein, crude fat, carbohydrate, and ash.

Determination of moisture and dry matter:

Moisture contents in the samples before and after formulation were determined by AOAC (2002), and dry matter of the sample and after formulation was estimated by drying the formulation in a hot-air oven at 100–105 °C till a constant weight, the percentage of moisture content in the sample was calculated using the following formula:

Moisture (%) = (weight of original sample minus weight of dried sample)/weight of original sample x 100

Dry matter (%) = 100-moisture (%)

Determination of crude protein:

Nitrogen in the samples was estimated by the Micro-Kjeldhal method and multiplied by the factor 6.25 to get the value of crude protein.

Nitrogen (%) = Value of H₂SO₄ x 0.1 x 0.014/Weight of sample x 100

Crude protein (%) = nitrogen (%) x conversion factor

Where the conversion factor for animal and plant origin is 6.25 and 5.90, respectively.

Determination of crude lipid:

Lipid was examined with a low-boiling organic solvent (petroleum ether, 40–60°C) by Soxhlet extraction, and the extract was thus weighted after the recovery of the solvent. Crude lipid was determined through the Soxhlet extraction technique. The crude lipid percentage (%) was calculated using the following formula:

Crude lipid (%) = corrected weight of lipid/weight of sample X100

Determination of Ash:

It was estimated by the sample in the muffle furnace at 600–650 °C. The ash content of each formulation was estimated by following the incineration method.

Ash (%) = Weight of Ash/Weight of Sample X100

Determination of crude fiber:

Crude fiber was estimated by successive boiling of a lipid-free sample with a 1.25% sulfuric acid solution and then with a 0.25% sodium hydroxide solution. The crude fiber content of feed ingredients was then determined according to the following formula:

Crude fiber (%) = (Wt. of crucible dried residue) - (Wt. of crucible with ashed sample)/Wt. of original sample×100

Determination of carbohydrate:

Carbohydrate was determined by the difference between the original weight of the sample and the sum of the weights of its moisture; crude protein (CP), crude fat (CF), ash, and crude fiber were determined by their appropriate analysis.

Carbohydrate (%) = 100 (moisture + ash + fiber + crude protein + crude fat).

Mineral Analysis:

Mineral contents of the complementary foods were determined by atomic absorption spectrometry (Iron (Fe), Zinc (Zn), Calcium (Ca), Manganese (Mn), Copper (Cu) and Magnesium (Mg) while sodium and potassium were determined using flame photometer.

Anti-Nutritional Analysis

Anti-nutritional compounds such as phytate, tannin, and oxalate were determined before and after fermentation. Two grams of each sample were weighed into 250 ml of 2% hydrochloric acid, which was used to soak each sample in a conical flask for 3 hours.

Phytate

The phytate content of the samples was determined by the method described by Vaintraub and Lapteva (1988). About 1.0 g of sample were extracted with 10 ml of 0.2 N HCl for 1 h, followed by 30 min of centrifugation at 3000 rpm. To 3 ml of the supernatant solution, 2 ml of Wade reagent were added, and the mixture was centrifuged. The absorbance at 500 nm was measured using an ultra violet spectrophotometer (Lambda 950) (Thermo Scientific Model Evolution 220, USA). (Dilebo *et al.*, 2023)

Tannin

Tannin content was determined using the Burns method, as modified by Maxson and Rooney (1978). The extracted supernatant solutions from 1 g of the sample were mixed with 5 ml of vanillin-HCl reagent after centrifuging at 1000 rpm for 5 min. After the reaction was accomplished, the absorbance was measured using a spectrophotometer at 500 nm. (Dilebo *et al.*, 2023)

Oxalate

The oxalate content of the sample was determined using the procedures described by Ukpabi and Ejidoh (1989). Which include three steps: digestion, oxalate precipitation, and permanganate titration. (Dilebo *et al.*, 2023)

Statistical analysis

The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using IBM SPSS, version 27. 0 Values were represented as mean + standard error mean (SEM) and compared using post hoc multiple comparisons at the 0.05 level of significance.

Millet and Soybeans Weaning Formulated Diet at Different Proportions

Millet were cleaned and washed to remove stones and other debris, then soaked in water for 12 hour to ferment. After fermentation, the millet was drained and milled until a fine paste was obtained. The paste was filtered through a 250µm sieve with added water to aid the process, separating the liquid from the chaff. The sieved millet paste was allowed to rest for 8 hours, and then the clear water on top was drained. The thick paste was mixed with water to form a thick slurry. Boiled water was gently poured over the slurry. Soybeans was cleaned, removing stones and other debris, then washed and dried, and roasted in an oven at 350°F (175°C) until they emitted a fragrant aroma and turned lightly golden brown. And were then milled into a fine powder, and the soybeans powder was gradually added while continuously stirring to prevent the formation of lumps. The mixture was simmered over low heat for 5-10 minutes until it thickened to the desired consistency, and it was preserved in an airtight container until it was used for analysis. The composition of the formulated diet of millet and soybeans is shown in Table 1. The food samples were mixed in the following proportions, that is, 70.2% of millet and 29.8% of soybeans to obtain A1. 68.2% millet and 31.8% soybeans to obtain B1, while 36.2% millet and 63.8% soybeans were mixed to obtain C1 sample.

Table 1: Millet and Soybeans Weaning Formulated Diet at Different Proportions:

SAMPLE	MILLET	SOYBEANS	RATIOS
A1 6–12	70.2%	29.8%	2.4 : 1
B1 12–24	68.2%	31.8%	2.1 : 1
C1 24–A	36.2%	63.8%	1 : 1.8

A1=06 to 12m, B1=12 to 24m, C1=24Above month.

Second Weaning formulated Diet at Different Proportions (groundnut and sorghum)

Sorghum were cleaned and washed to remove stones and other debris, then soaked in water for 12 hours to ferment. After fermentation, the sorghum was drained and milled until a fine paste was obtained. The paste was filtered through a 250µm sieve with added water to aid the process, separating the liquid from the chaff. The sieved sorghum paste was allowed to rest for 8 hours, and then the clear water on top was drained. And Groundnuts was cleaned, washed, and dried before were roasted in an oven at 350°F (175°C) for 15-20 minutes until fragrant and lightly golden brown. After cooling, the skins were removed by rubbing the nuts between the hands, and the roasted, skinned groundnuts were blended with water to achieve a smooth, creamy consistency. In a separate pot, water was boiled, and the thick groundnut paste was mixed with water to create a thick slurry, then added to the boiled water and cooked for 10-15 minutes. Additionally, the sorghum paste, mention above was added to thicken the boiled groundnut paste, which was cooked for an additional 5 minutes. And it was preserved in an airtight container until it was used for analysis. The composition of the formulated diet of groundnut and sorghum is shown in Table 2. The food samples were mixed in the following proportions, that is, 42.3% of groundnut and 57.7% of sorghum to obtain A2. 44% groundnut and 56% sorghum to obtain B2, while 61.2% of groundnut and 38.8% sorghum were mixed to obtain C2 sample.

Table 2: Second Weaning formulated Diet at Different Proportions (groundnut and sorghum):

SAMPLE	GROUNDNUT	SORGHUM	RATIOS
A2 6–12	42.3%	57.7%	1 : 1.4
B2 12–24	44%	56%	1 : 2.3
C2 24–A	61.2%	38.8%	2.3 : 1

A2=06 to 12m, B2=12 to 24m, C2=24Above month.

RESULT

Result of Proximate Composition of the Formulated Weaning Diets

The results of proximate composition of formulated diets is presented in Table 6. The result showed that the diet formulated based on millet/soybeans and groundnut/sorghum. Ceralac has the higher moisture content ($11.3 \pm 0.5\%$) Sample A1 has ($10.34 \pm 0.16\%$) followed by Sample A2 ($8.29 \pm 0.19\%$) and there was no significant difference between Sample C1 ($3.60 \pm 0.38\%$) and C2 ($3.25 \pm 0.22\%$). There was no significant difference in ash content compared for both Sample. The result also shows significant difference in crude lipid content between all Samples which decreases from sample C1 ($13.65 \pm 0.12\%$) to sample B1 ($10.45 \pm 0.29\%$) and Sample A1 ($9.57 \pm 0.12\%$) having the least. No significant difference in crude fiber content was observed between all Samples, The protein contents of experimental food samples were significantly lower when compared with the ceralac (a commercial formula) samples. Sample C1 shows a significantly higher crude protein content ($22.31 \pm 0.22\%$) compared to both Sample, and followed by sample C2 ($19.27 \pm 0.20\%$) and there was no significant difference between sample B1, B2 and A1, A2 ($13.61 \pm 0.09\%$), ($13.47 \pm 0.30\%$) and ($12.60 \pm 0.23\%$), ($12.52 \pm 0.18\%$) respectively. Sample C2 has the lowest total carbohydrate content ($49.79 \pm 0.28\%$), significantly lower than both Sample, no significant different exist between sample A2, B1 and B2, and Sample A1 has ($62.52 \pm 0.71\%$).

TABLE 6: Proximate Composition of the formulated weaning diet

Sample	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Fiber (%)	Crude Lipids (%)	Crude Protein (%)	Carbohydrate (%)
A1	10.34 ± 0.16^b	2.56 ± 0.30^a	2.40 ± 0.24^b	9.57 ± 0.12^b	12.52 ± 0.18^a	62.52 ± 0.71^b
B1	7.25 ± 0.18^a	3.48 ± 0.30^a	1.47 ± 0.33^a	10.45 ± 0.29^b	13.61 ± 0.09^a	63.73 ± 0.70^a
C1	3.60 ± 0.38^a	2.49 ± 0.31^b	3.37 ± 0.21^b	13.65 ± 0.12^b	22.31 ± 0.22^b	54.58 ± 0.26^b
A2	8.29 ± 0.19^b	2.33 ± 0.16^a	2.45 ± 0.34^a	10.66 ± 0.23^b	12.60 ± 0.23^a	63.92 ± 0.11^a
B2	5.62 ± 0.19^b	3.51 ± 0.34^a	1.59 ± 0.22^b	12.47 ± 0.16^b	13.47 ± 0.30^a	63.38 ± 0.26^a
C2	3.25 ± 0.22^a	3.20 ± 0.73^b	2.30 ± 0.19^a	22.19 ± 0.31^b	19.27 ± 0.20^b	49.79 ± 0.28^b
Ceralac	9.30 ± 0.5^a	1.9 ± 0.10^a	1.7 ± 0.20^a	10.6 ± 0.30^a	21.9 ± 1.50^b	54.6 ± 3.80^a

Values are means \pm SD of duplicate determinations. Sample A1= Millet/Soybean 2.4:1 Pap, Sample B1= Millet/Soybean 2.1:1 Pap, Sample C1= Millet/Soybean 1:1.8 Pap. Sample A2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:1.4 Pap, Sample B2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:2.3 Pap, Sample C2= Groundnut/Sorghum 2.3:1 Pap. A1, A2= 06 to 12m, B1, B2= 12 to 24m and C1, C2=24Above month infant. Values with the same letter are not significantly different, while those with different letters are significantly different.

Result of Mineral Analysis of the Formulated weaning diet

Table 7 represents the mineral content of formulated diet A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, and C2. A1 was Cu 11.69 ± 0.009^b , Fe 102.39 ± 0.007^b , Zn 3.32 ± 0.016^a , Mg 11.67 ± 0.034^a , K 108.09 ± 0.18^a , Ca 88.33 ± 0.22^b . A2 had Cu of 15.80 ± 0.011^a , Fe of 53.97 ± 0.015^b , Zn of 3.24 ± 0.029^b , Mg of 12.16 ± 0.040^a , K of 139.48 ± 0.20^b , and Ca of 157.58 ± 0.12^b . While the B1 were Cu 12.52 ± 0.007^b , Fe 124.67 ± 0.013^a , Zn 3.84 ± 0.018^b , Mg 12.63 ± 0.023^b , K 115.32 ± 0.16^a , and Ca 95.24 ± 0.16^b . And B2 Cu 14.48 ± 0.012^a , Fe 71.96 ± 0.016^b , Zn 3.91 ± 0.020^a , Mg 12.75 ± 0.033^a , K 142.17 ± 0.19^b , and Ca 161.97 ± 0.18^a . The results also show that C1 had Cu, Fe, Zn, Mg, K, and Ca values of 22.85 ± 0.007^b , 214.38 ± 0.023^b , 4.86 ± 0.011^a , 19.50 ± 0.016^a , 200.66 ± 0.10^a , 187.91 ± 0.21^a , and C2 17.99 ± 0.011^b , 117.53 ± 0.013^a , 5.20 ± 0.024^a , 16.87 ± 0.043^a , 158.33 ± 0.15^a , and 189.25 ± 0.31^a respectively.

TABLE 7: Minerals Analysis of the Formulated weaning diet

Sample	Cu (ppm)	Fe (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Mg (ppm)	K (ppm)	Ca (ppm)
A1	11.69± 0.009 ^b	102.39± 0.017 ^b	3.32± 0.016 ^a	11.67± 0.034 ^a	108.09± 0.18 ^a	88.33± 0.22 ^b
B1	12.52 ± 0.007 ^b	124.67 ± 0.013 ^a	3.84 ± 0.018 ^b	12.63 ± 0.023 ^b	115.32 ± 0.16 ^a	95.24 ± 0.16 ^b
C1	22.85 ± 0.007 ^b	214.38 ± 0.023 ^b	4.86 ± 0.011 ^a	19.50 ± 0.016 ^a	200.66 ± 0.10 ^a	187.91 ± 0.21 ^a
A2	15.80 ± 0.011 ^a	53.97 ± 0.015 ^b	3.24 ± 0.029 ^b	12.16 ± 0.040 ^a	139.48 ± 0.20 ^b	157.58 ± 0.12 ^b
B2	14.48 ± 0.012 ^a	71.96 ± 0.016 ^b	3.91 ± 0.020 ^a	12.75 ± 0.033 ^a	142.17 ± 0.19 ^b	161.97 ± 0.18 ^a
C2	17.99 ± 0.011 ^b	117.53 ± 0.013 ^a	5.20 ± 0.024 ^a	16.87 ± 0.043 ^a	158.33 ± 0.15 ^a	189.25 ± 0.31 ^a
Ceralac	0.00 ± 000 ^b	7.5 ± 0.00 ^a	5.00 ± 0.000 ^a	0.00 ± 000 ^a	635.0 ± 0.01 ^a	600.0 ± 0.1 ^b

All values are represented as mean ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations. Sample A1= Millet/Soybean 2.4:1 Pap, Sample B1= Millet/Soybean 2.1:1 Pap, Sample C1= Millet/Soybean 1:1.8 Pap. Sample A2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:1.4 Pap, Sample B2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:2.3 Pap, Sample C2= Groundnut/Sorghum 2.3:1 Pap. A1, A2= 06 to 12m, B1, B2= 12 to 24m and C1, C2=24Above month infant. Values with the same letter are not significantly different, while those with different letters are significantly different.

Result of Anti-nutritional factor of the Formulated weaning diet

Table 8 represents the anti-nutritional factor of A1, A2, B1, B2, C1 and C2 samples. The level of the oxalate was 8.45±0.27, 4.94±0.14, 6.64±0.53, 3.60±0.36, 5.01±0.71 and 2.93±0.39, 2.62±0.35 respectively, for tannin A1 and A2 has 2.42±0.42, 1.56±0.22. B1 and B2 has 3.25±0.43, 1.38±0.27. While C1 and C2 has 3.10±0.68, 1.20±0.42. The result also shows A1, A2, B1, B2, C1 and C2 had 0.19±0.20, 0.09±0.61, 0.15±0.34, 0.06±0.32, 0.11±0.51, and 0.05±0.29 respectively.

TABLE 8: Anti-Nutritional factor of the Formulated weaning diet

Sample	Oxalate (mg/100g)	Tannin (mg/100g)	Phytate (mg/100g)
A1	8.45 ± 0.27 ^b	2.42 ± 0.42 ^a	0.19 ± 0.20 ^a
B1	6.64 ± 0.53 ^b	3.25 ± 0.43 ^a	0.15 ± 0.34 ^a
C1	5.02 ± 0.71 ^b	3.10 ± 0.68 ^a	0.11 ± 0.51 ^a
A2	4.94 ± 0.14 ^a	1.56 ± 0.22 ^b	0.09 ± 0.61 ^a
B2	3.60 ± 0.36 ^b	1.38 ± 0.27 ^a	0.06 ± 0.32 ^a
C2	2.93 ± 0.39 ^a	1.20 ± 0.42 ^b	0.05 ± 0.29 ^a

All values are represented as mean ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations. Sample A1= Millet/Soybean 2.4:1 Pap, Sample B1= Millet/Soybean 2.1:1 Pap, Sample C1= Millet/Soybean 1:1.8 Pap. Sample A2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:1.4 Pap, Sample B2= Groundnut/Sorghum 1:2.3 Pap, Sample C2= Groundnut/Sorghum 2.3:1 Pap. A1, A2= 06 to 12m, B1, B2= 12 to 24m and C1, C2=24Above month infant. Values with the same letter are not significantly different, while those with different letters are significantly different.

DISCUSSION

Proximate Composition of formulated weaning diet

Traditional cereals and leguminous crops are significant components of the diets of numerous individuals in Africa and Asia. They serve as primary sources of proteins, carbohydrates and minerals, forming the basis of traditional weaning foods (Anigo *et al.*, 2010). Sample A1 had relatively high moisture contents; low protein and lipid contents; and unvaried crude fiber and ash composition, when compared to the rest of the samples, inclusions of soybean and groundnut in higher percent and reduction of millet and sorghum caused significant reduction in moisture content and increase in the protein and lipid contents. The result also revealed that Dry matter content of the Complementary foods decreases from sample A1 (10.34±0.16) sample C1 (3.60±0.38) and sample C2 (3.25±0.22), indicating significant higher solid content in the latter C1 and C2. This may be due to the higher addition of soybeans and groundnut, which contribute to a denser texture. The reason behind the food samples' comparatively reduced moisture content could be attributed to processes involved in processing methods. The sample differ significantly in their lipid, and protein content, Values which correlates with the proximate characteristics of the

soybean and groundnut results in sustained moisture level; increased protein and lipid content and lowered carbohydrate values of the formulated diet. This is also characteristics of soybeans and groundnut as observed in Table 3. Here the result obtained for moisture, lipid, protein and carbohydrate values are different to each other. This indicates that while processing does not affect the composition of the major macro nutrients, protein, lipid and carbohydrates, the soybeans and groundnut may add to the lipid and protein values and also diminish the ash content. Inclusion of the food staples soybean and groundnut add nutritive value. Although The inclusion of protein-rich ingredients such as soybeans and groundnut in formulation enhances the protein and fat content of the foods, potentially offering greater nutritional benefits for infants and young children. The crude lipid levels observed in the formulated complementary food sample A1 (Table 6) were below the recommended daily allowance (RDA) of 10 to 30% for infants 06 to 12 month, as suggested by Anigo *et al.* (2010). Although it meet the crude protein recommended daily allowance (RDA) for infants, The result also revealed that the crude protein of all sample observed in the formulated complementary foods (Table 6) meet the recommended daily allowance (RDA) for infants, as suggested by Anigo *et al.*, (2010) except C2 for 24 and above month.. These indicate that diet formulated are good source of protein that can prevent protein energy malnutrition. However, the protein contents of experimental food samples were significantly lower when compared with the cerelac (a commercial formula) samples. Investigations have shown that protein content of cereal- legume combination (i.e., two or more plant-based food materials) is better than those produced from cereal (i.e., a single plant based food materials) (Solomon, 2000; Achi, 2005; Wakil and Onilude, 2009). Nutritionally, the protein contents value of the experimental food samples met the FAO/WHO (1991) specification guidelines for the young child complementary food formulations. In comparison, the nutrient-dense of formulated food samples was lower than that of the traditional complementary foods that characterize with low energy and nutrient density (King and Ahworth, 1987) and they were comparable to the commercial formulas (Cerelac).

The result also revealed that all sample meet the required carbohydrate composition. For the body's metabolic processes, carbohydrates are a readily available source of metabolic fuel (Adesuyi *et al.*, 2012; Hemagowda *et al.*, 2019) all the formulated diet could serve as a diet base in the weaning foods for infant. 06 to 12, 12 to 24 and 24 and above month.

Minerals Analysis of the Formulated weaning diet

The mineral composition of the formulated food sample presented in Table 7 showed that potassium was the highest mineral in ceralac (635.0 ± 0.01^a), while copper (0.00 ± 000^b) was the least in ceralac sample. In comparisons, the mineral contents of the formulated food samples were higher when compared with the complementary food sample of cerelac and FAO/WHO (1991) recommended values. The variation in mineral content of formulated food samples with that of cerelac (a commercial formula) could be due to the enrichment of the cerelac product with essential mineral during production. This observation indicates that the formulated food samples would serve as good sources of minerals such as calcium and phosphorous, which are considered essential for bone and teeth formation and development in children (Nieman *et al.*, 1992). This indicates that the formulated food sample were suitable as complementary food for infants with immature heart. Potassium has a beneficial effect on sodium balance. A high intake of potassium has been reported to protect against increasing blood pressure and other cardiovascular risks (Langford 1983; Cappuccio and McGregor, 1991). Hence, the sodium to potassium (Na/K) ratio in the body is of great concern for the prevention of high blood pressure. A Na/K ratio less than one is recommended in the diets of people who are prone to high blood pressure and similarly for children with immature heart (Langford 1983; Cappuccio and McGregor, 1991).

The mineral composition of complementary foods plays a crucial role in addressing nutritional deficiencies and promoting optimal growth and development, especially in resource-limited settings (Rashida *et al.*, 2014). Calcium stands as a crucial micronutrient vital for infants and young children, facilitating bone and teeth development, muscle and nerve function, blood clotting, and immune defense mechanisms (Rashida *et al.*, 2014). The Calcium content shows a consistent increase in levels from sample A1 88.33 ± 0.22 to sample C2 189.25 ± 0.31 . Anigo *et al.*, (2009) reported that the addition of legumes, such as soybeans, can enhance the calcium content of complementary foods. According to

FAO/WHO (2001; Anigo *et al.*, 2010), cereals generally have low levels of minerals such as iron and zinc. However, the inclusion of legumes can effectively increase the iron content. The soybeans and groundnut inclusion in the formulated diet resulted in significantly higher contents of calcium, and iron. Although diet formulation may have diminished the levels of these parameters, this corresponds to the result obtained for soybeans and groundnut in Table 7. The body relies on a consistent supply of zinc from daily diets, and enhancing the zinc content in the diet, as achieved in the formulated complementary foods, could potentially reduce the prevalence of stunting in the region (Anigo *et al.*, 2010), FAO/WHO (2001) noted that zinc supply can impact linear growth, emphasizing its importance in addressing stunting. According to Onabanjo (2007), zinc is a crucial element in the structure of nearly 100 different enzymes and is essential for approximately 200 different enzymes. It appears to play a vital role in all major metabolic pathways (Oyegoke *et al.*, 2020). The zinc content of all the formulated foods is lower than the recommended dietary allowance (RDA) value of 6 mg/100g, as outlined by the Codex Alimentarius Guidelines for formulated supplementary foods for older infants and young children (Oyegoke; 2020, FAO/WHO, 1991). The zinc contribution of groundnut was maintained, the diet formulation and processing method may have affected availability of zinc in soybean as reported Compounds such as tannins, phytate, oxalate and proteins have been identified as affecting the bioavailability of zinc (Coulibaly *et al.*, 2011; Popova and Mihaylova, 2019; Sheethal *et al.*, 2022). Iron is recognized as a vital element in red blood cell formation (Oyegoke *et al.*, 2020). Its insufficiency is thought to impact a significant portion of the global population, estimated to range from 20% to 50%, thus rendering it the most prevalent micronutrient deficiency worldwide (Onabanjo, 2007). In the weaning period, the Iron requirements in relation to energy intake are at their peak throughout the lifespan. The rapidly growing weaning infant lacks Iron stores and must depend on dietary Iron alone, according to FAO/WHO (2001). These deficiencies may be attributed to either nutrient loss during processing or insufficient micronutrient content in plant-based diets (Solomon, 2005). Potassium, much like sodium, is an electrolyte that plays a vital role in regulating the balance of body fluids (Oyegoke *et al.*, 2020). Significant differences were observed in the copper values obtained in the study. A significant difference was obtained in the magnesium content which ranged between 11.67mg/100g-19.5mg/100g. These minerals are crucial for a range of bodily functions, and consuming foods abundant in manganese and magnesium, can support overall health and vitality.

Anti-Nutritional factor of Formulated diet

The results showed that the mean phytate for all the samples are not statistically significant compared to one another, the trend showed A1> B1> C1>A2>B2>C2. A1 has high phytate, due to high concentration of millet in the formulation, followed by B1 and C1, which may prevent its absorption. Other minerals including zinc, are also chelated by phytate (Adesuyi *et al.*, 2012). The oxalate determination showed highest composition of oxalate in the A1, B1, and C1. The lowest oxalate was observed in C2, B2 and A1. The trend C2> B2 > soybeans A2. Kidney stones, electrolyte imbalances, and digestive tract discomfort in humans are caused by the anti-nutrient oxalate (Egbuna and Ifemeje, 2015). Oxalates have an impact on the metabolism of calcium and magnesium. They also interact with proteins to create complexes that slow the process of peptic digestion (Akande *et al.*, 2010). The result also revealed that B1 has the highest tannin followed by C1 and A1, for A2, B2 and C2 are having almost near value. Thus, the results revealed that the anti-nutrient composition of all formulated diet were generally low such that none of the anti-nutrients was above the lethal dosage approved by standard bodies like National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC) in Nigeria. The reason behind the diet samples' comparatively reduced oxalate, tannin and phytate content could be attributed to processes involved in processing methods.

CONCLUSION

This study aim to develop and evaluate a dietary weaning formula using millet, soybeans, groundnut and sorghum in ratios as an alternative dietary formulation source for weaning. The results highlight the macro and micronutrient of the weaning-formulated local diets, as well as assessing the levels of anti-nutritional factors in the weaning formulated local diets,

Lastly the research evaluated the effect of processing method of the weaning-formulated local diet which comparatively reduced the level of anti-nutritional factor and formulated diet were good sources of high quality of protein and energy values. Nutritionally, that can prevent protein Energy malnutrition.

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